

EXAMINING LINKAGE BETWEEN MEDIATING ROLE OF AFFILIATIVE GROUP COHESIVENESS ON DEMAND-ABILITY-FIT AND TURNOVER INTENTION

BAHARUDIN^{1*}, SULASTRI², ISNURHADI³ and ZUNAIDAH⁴

¹Ph.D Student of Doctoral of Management Science Program, Universitas Sriwijaya, Indonesia. Correspondent Email: baharuddin.unsri@gmail.com

^{2,3,4}Doctoral Program of Management Science, Universitas Sriwijaya, Indonesia. Email: sulastrisri@unsri.ac.id², isnurhadi2020@gmail.com³, zunaidah66@yahoo.com⁴

Abstract

Focus of this study is investigate the examining linkage the Affiliate group cohesiveness (AGC) contributes to the turnover intention (TI) of nurses in private hospitals and has a positive impact on increasing the demand ability-fit (DAF) nurses. Based on the social exchange theory, this study explores the effect of DAF on turnover intention and the role of affiliative group cohesiveness as a mediator. A cross-sectional study was conducted on 185 nurses working in private hospitals in South Sumatra Province, serving in the emergency room, operating room, ICU, and inpatient care. The nurse completes the online questionnaire with a google form to see the effect of each variable. Hypothesis testing and statistical description using SmartPLS v3 and SPSS 26. The results revealed that AGC had a negative and significant impact on TI. DAF does not affect on TI. AGC partially mediates the effect between DAF and TI. The results of this study indicate the critical role of AGC in increasing demand for personal fitness abilities and reducing nurse turnover intention.

Keywords: Affiliative Group Cohesiveness, Demand-Ability-Fit, Turnover Intention

1. Introduction

Turnover intention (TI) research has become one of the trendy topics in human resource management since the 20th century, and thousands of qualitative and quantitative studies have been published (Iqbal et al., 2020; Jin et al., 2016; Li & Sawhney, 2019). Human resource management strategies play an essential role in reducing TI (Iqbal et al., 2020). Most studies discuss the impact (Lee et al., 2012) and antecedents of TI on organizations (Wang, 2018). The issue of TI has received substantial attention from managers and academics because of its impact on organizational performance (Li & Sawhney, 2019). TI research is also actively carried out in the nursing field (Sheehan et al., 2019) and is a significant problem (Alhamwan et al., 2015; Nantsupawat et al. 2017); as well as a global issue in hospital management (Busari et al., 2017). Nurses are a profession with the highest proportion of hospital workers, around 40-60% of health workers, and they absorb more than 50% of the budget (Rindu et al., 2018). Nurses are directly involved in almost all aspects of hospital quality, including patient care, therapeutics, surgery, data collection, and reporting. Nursing services have a significant share of in-hospital services and require greater attention from hospital management (Sari et al., 2018).

Previous studies have shown that the percentage of nurses' TI globally is more than 50%, such as the research of Chen et al. (2018) stated that the TI of nurses in Jiangsu province, China was 50.2%; Taiwan, 56.1% (Lee et al., 2017); and 54.1% in Pennsylvania hospitals, United States (DiMattio & Spegman, 2019). The last few years have seen an increase in nurse TI in Indonesia. The study of Suyono et al. (2018) showed that 60% of nurses working in type C hospitals in Batam stated their intention to change jobs; the study of Mardiana et al. (2014) found that 57% of nurses working at Dhuafa Hospital in Bogor intend to leave their jobs. Asmara (2017) stated that 50.8% of Surabaya Surgical Hospital nurses intend to leave their jobs. According to Cohen et al. (2016), the possibility of TI is an actual turnover of 59%, meaning that more than 25% of nurses will leave their jobs; theoretically, the maximum turnover of nurses in hospitals is between 5% and 10% in a year (Gillies, 1994; Mardiana et al., 2014). One of the TI studies that has received attention is the study of the effect of demand ability fit on TI (Abdalla et al., 2018; Peng et al., 2014). Published research results show different findings (Abdalla et al., 2018; Peng et al., 2014; Sylva et al., 2019). The studies of Abdalla et al. (2018) and Peng et al. (2014) explain how demand for the ability fit (DAF) through various placement processes is expected to decrease TI in an organization. Unfortunately, the results of empirical studies prove differences in the findings.

The results of the Kerse study (2018) confirm that DAF shows a positive correlation with job satisfaction, commitment, performance, stress reduction, and decreased turnover; this is due to the match between individual and environmental characteristics (Ostroff & Schulte, 2007). This opinion is supported by research findings that DAF has a negative and significant influence on TI (Rajper et al., 2020; Sylva et al., 2019). On the other hand, several studies argue that there is no significant correlation between DAF and TI; this lies in the work setting in the organization and the culture of the individual (Abdalla et al., 2018; Choi et al., 2017). The research findings on DAF, and TI cannot be concluded with certainty. Therefore, the model in this study is intended to solve the empirical gap between DAF and TI by placing affiliate group cohesiveness as a mediating variable. Based on the social exchange theory, Affiliative group cohesiveness (AGC) is an essential element of social exchange as a consideration for staying or leaving the group (Homans, 1958; Lee et al., 2012). According to this theory, individuals who are treated with respect and benefit have better self-perceptions (Lawler, 2001; Roberts, 2007) and are more likely to reciprocate in kind (Lawler, 2001), such as remaining in the organization (Almaaitah et al., 2017). The research model was tested empirically on nurses working in type C private hospitals in South Sumatra Province, serving in the Emergency Room, Operating Room, Inpatient, and ICU.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Social Exchanged Theory

The main idea in social exchange theory (SET) is that the parties involved in an exchange relationship expect to result from the interaction (Blau, 1964; Homans, 1958; Miles, 2012). According to Homans (1958), there are two essential variables in SET, namely, first cohesiveness, which is defined as everything that attracts someone to be part of a group, and second, communication, better known as interaction, which is a measure of the frequency of

verbal behavior. The main reasons for the exchange are maximizing benefits, minimizing costs, and ending or abandoning relationships when the risks outweigh the rewards (Cherry, 2010). Exchange leads to more outstanding organizational commitment and triggers the desire to stay in the organization by reducing TI (Harden et al., 2016). Groups with high cohesiveness (AGC) will appear more favorable when compared to groups that are less cohesive due to social exchanges such as behavior to help others (Khalid et al., 2020). Researchers have widely adopted the SET in discussing the issue of TI (Ali Memon et al., 2014; Harden et al., 2016; Paul & Kee, 2020; Self et al., 2020). Paul and Kee (2020) stated that social exchange significantly affects human resources and TI.

2.2 Demand Ability Fit (DAF) and Turnover Intention (TI)

Theoretically, DAF is one of the dimensions of a person-job fit (Abdalla, 2018; Resick et al., 2007) and is an essential aspect of employee work. The excess or lack of fulfillment of job requirements has a negative impact on employees (Park et al., 2012). DAF to reflect the compatibility between job requirements, knowledge, skills, and employees' abilities (Peng et al., 2014). Previous studies explained that personal employee factors, including professional competence (Numminen et al., 2016), suitability of job demands with abilities (Peng et al., 2014), and group cohesiveness (Nelsey & Brownie, 2012), could trigger TI. The accumulation of various factors that trigger turnover intention is job dissatisfaction, which impacts the decision to stay or leave the organization (Belete, 2018). Individual decisions to leave the organization have a financial impact and are also related to the loss of the organization's competitive advantage (Uğural et al., 2020). The majority of research results state that turnover intention is a proxy for actual turnover (Menezes et al., 2018). DAF plays a vital role in organizations, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, TI, and overall organizational performance (Kristof-Brown, 2005; Dineen et al., 2018; Sylva et al., 2019). DAF is associated with work behaviors such as performance, stress, and turnover intention (Park et al., 2012). In the study results, Sylva et al. (2019) concluded that individuals with low levels of perceived DAF tend to change jobs and take a long time to increase DAF compared to individuals with high levels of perceived DAF. DAF leads to more positive outcomes such as higher job satisfaction, increased performance, and decreased TI (Beier et al., 2019). In contrast, individuals with low demand ability tend to display poor performance, increased turnover, and absenteeism (Hassan et al., 2012). The positive correlation between DAF and intrinsic satisfaction impacts job satisfaction (Dineen et al., 2018) and impacts lower TI (Nguyen et al., 2020).

H1= Demands ability to fit have a significant effect on turnover intention.

2.3 Demand Ability fit (DAF) and Affiliative Group Cohesiveness (AGC)

The atmosphere of a cohesive work environment affects individual performance (Bruhn, 2009; Hall, 2001). Individual contributions to work are high if there is a match between abilities and job demands and support from a work environment that facilitates the application of abilities and skills (Crom et al., 2018). The match between abilities and demands will create a work unit that is more cohesive and functions more effectively (Werbel

et al., 2001). DAF positively affects social cohesion and group performance (Seong et al., 2012), correlated with job quality and individual involvement in organizational activities (Crom et al., 2018). Matching will create cohesiveness in unit work and effectively make the unit work more functional (Werbel et al., 2001). According to Shin et al. (2009), AGC strengthens group competence to achieve better group performance. The atmosphere of a cohesive work environment affects individual performance (Bruhn, 2009; Hall, 2001). Individual contributions to work will be higher if there is a match between abilities and job demands and support from a work environment that facilitates the application of abilities and skills (Crom et al., 2018).

H2= Demands ability to fit have a significant effect on affiliate group cohesiveness.

2.4 Affiliative Group Cohesiveness (AGC) and Turnover Intention (TI)

Groups with high cohesiveness facilitate affiliation (Cornwell & Dokhsin, 2014). AGC is one of the essential factors in group performance (Huang, 2009). Groups can become stronger and more successful if the environment in the organization is built cohesively (Al-Rawi, 2008; Lee et al., 2012). Cohesiveness impacts satisfaction within the group so that the group can achieve the agreed goals (Bozic, 2018; Steinhardt, 2003). AGC is less than 75% so individuals may leave the organization (Asegid et al., 2014). Individual affiliation behavior in organizations increases work effectiveness by maintaining and improving interpersonal relationships and work procedures (He et al., 2017). Support from colleagues has been shown to increase nurses' intention to stay (Guchait et al., 2016). AGC is one of the determinants of the organization's internal work environment and contributes to TI (Gupta & Shaheen, 2017; Kang et al., 2017). An organizational atmosphere with high cohesiveness has been shown to reduce TI (Lee et al., 2012), and AGC is a significant predictor of TI (Asegid et al., 2014).

H3= Affiliative group cohesiveness have a significant effect on affects turnover intention.

2.5 Affiliative Group Cohesiveness as mediating variable

In nursing practice, group cohesiveness can help reduce work frustration and TI (Lee et al., 2012). Modifying AGC empirically helps retain nurses in an organization (Asegid et al., 2014). Khan and Qadir (2016) stated that high cohesiveness significantly reduces TI. Workgroups that lack cohesion impedes performance, reduce productivity, increase group conflict, decrease job satisfaction, and increase absenteeism (Carver & Candela, 2008). In this research, AGC is defined as the desire to build work and social relations that are mutually binding between group members, characterized by interest, a sense of belonging, and being part of a group to achieve common goals. Group affiliation can occur if cohesiveness is formed among group members (Cornwell & Dokshin, 2014). High group cohesiveness implies a more substantial level of group bonding (Ghosh et al., 2019). One of the essential factors for creating group success is high group cohesiveness because it affects group performance (Beal et al., 2003). AGC develops along with group cooperation in achieving goals (Dziecielak, 2020). Cohesiveness is an essential requirement for effective

teamwork (Ghosh et al., 2019), as a dynamic force that allows team members to attract each other and work together to achieve team goals (Lee et al., 2012). Many experts and researchers have carried out studies on AGC and TI (Abdillah, 2012; Huang, 2009; Speer et al., 2001; Tung et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2005; Williams et al., 2006). This study explains that AGC has a negative effect on TI. A similar opinion was expressed by Lee et al. (2012) with their study of the relationship between organizational support, organizational commitment, and organizational cohesiveness on TI and found that AGC can reduce TI. AGC strengthens competencies (ability, knowledge, and skills) for achieving better group performance (Shin et al., 2009). Group cohesiveness has a negative effect on TI and mediates TI (Asegid et al., 2014).

H4= Affiliative group cohesiveness mediated negatively and significantly the effect of demands, fit, and turnover intention.

3. Research Design and Method

Data were collected from nurses who work in type C private hospitals on duty in the emergency department, operating room, ICU, and inpatient care in South Sumatra Province. Research permits were applied to 10 private type C hospitals in South Sumatra Province, but only six hospitals were granted research permits. The questionnaire instrument was distributed via Google Form to 240 nurses, and as many as 185 nurses gave answers. Nurses were asked to provide answers on a Likert scale. All instrument measurements are sourced from theory and previous research. Reliability and validity tests were carried out and obtained a Cronbach Alpha demand ability of 0.992, an affiliative group cohesiveness of 0.899, and a turnover intention of 0.825. Hypothesis and theory testing using the structural equation model method with SmartPLS v3 and SPSS-26 for the statistical description analysis. The measurement of the variable consists of three measurements of perception, namely, demand for ability fit (DAF), affiliative group cohesiveness (AGC), and turnover intention (TI). The measurement aims to collect demographic data, including gender, age, years of service, and education. The measurement of the DAF construct consists of seven items, namely "my nursing knowledge is suitable for the given task," "I have the knowledge needed to help advance the work unit," and "my education is following my job position as a nurse," "I have needed to help advance the work unit," "the work demands are following my expertise as a nurse," "my nursing skills contribute to the progress of the work unit," and "my abilities are following the needs of the hospital work unit." The measurement of the AGC construct consists of seven items, namely "group members unite in achieving common goals," "group members are free to communicate in carrying out tasks", "group members help each other to complete the assigned task," "I like the way my group runs tasks," "I like to help my friends work according to my ability," "I like to offer help to coworkers who are in trouble," and "I feel happy when I can lighten the burden of coworkers.". The measurement of the TI construct consists of 5 items, namely "I am thinking of leaving my current job immediately," "I am considering changing my profession," "I am trying to find work opportunities in other

hospitals," and "I am actively looking for new job information," and "I will change my place of work next year at the latest."

4. Result and Discussion

The study was conducted on 185 respondents working in a type C private hospital assigned to the emergency department, operating room, inpatient, and ICU, with as many as 153 female respondents and 32 male respondents aged 31-45 years, 101 and 80 respondents aged under 30 years. The majority of education levels are Diploma with 122 respondents and undergraduate with 63 respondents. 133 respondents with more than seven years of service and the remaining 52 respondents with less than seven years of service. The measurement of the structural model using the SmartPLS method is seen from the values of convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability (ρ_c), and Cronbach's Alpha. The convergent validity value is obtained from the analysis of external loadings demand ability to fit, affiliative group cohesiveness, and turnover intention with a value above 0.7. The results of the analysis of discriminant validity, composite reliability (c), and Cronbach's Alpha can be seen in Table 1:

Table 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Discriminant Vailidity (AVE)
Affiliative group cohesiveness	0.899	0.919	0.586
Demand ability fit	0.922	0.937	0.681
Turnover intention	0.825	0.875	0.584

Table 1 describes the results of the confirmatory factor analysis test with discriminant validity affiliative group cohesiveness values of 0.586, Cronbach's Alpha 0.899, and composite reliability of 0.919. The DAF discriminant validity have value is 0.681, Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.992, and composite reliability is 0.937. The TI has a discriminant validity value of 0.584, a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.825, and composite reliability of 0.875. The results of the discriminant validity test > 0.5 , the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values > 0.7 , indicating that all constructs have good validity and reliability. A multicollinearity test is needed to determine whether there are independent variables that have similarities between independent variables in a regression model. The multicollinearity test looks at the variance inflation factor (VIF) value, as shown in table 2. The value of variance inflation factor demand abilities fit affiliate group cohesiveness is 1,000. On the TI of 1,826, it can be concluded that there is no violation of the multicollinearity assumption.

Table 2. Multicollinearity Analysis of DAF, AGC and TI

Variables	Affiliative group cohesiveness	Turnover Intention
Affiliative group cohesiveness		1.826
Demand ability fit	1.000	1.826

Structural model analysis on SmartPLs includes goodness of fit tests, hypothesis tests, and path coefficients. The goodness of fit test analyzes the values of R squares, Q squares, and the NFI value. The hypothesis test used is the statistical t-test and p-value, while the path coefficient looks at each variable's direct and indirect effects. Testing the feasibility of the model to see if the model formed is suitable for research or not by looking at the results of the analysis of R-squares, Q-squares, and NFI can be seen in table 3.

Table 3. Goodness of fit Model

Variables	R Square	Q Squares [[1-R ₁ ²] x [(1-R ₂ ²)]	NFI
Affiliative group cohesiveness	0.452	0,999	0.881
Turnover intention	0.091		

Table 3 shows the influence of DAF on AGC of 0.452, or 45.2 percent. The magnitude of the influence of DAF on TI is 0.091, or 9.1 percent. Furthermore, from the results of the R-squares analysis, the Q square value is 0.999, meaning that the level of model diversity indicated by demand ability fit and affiliative group cohesiveness to turnover intention is 0.999 or 99.9 percent, and other factors still influence the remaining 0.001 or 0.1 percent. Another analysis needed to measure the goodness of the fit model is the value of the normed fit index (NFI). Based on the results of the analysis of the model fit indicators in table 3, the NFI value of 0.881, which is greater than 0.1, means that the model is declared good. The data analyzed through testing the PLS algorithm and bootstrapping is used to test the hypothesis. From the results of path analysis, it can be concluded that the model in this research variable has a path coefficient value of positive and negative influence, as shown in table 5.

Table 4. Results of Path Coefficients Analisis Analisis

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
Affiliaitve group cohesiveness → Turnover intention	-0.347	3.468	0.001*
Demand ability fit → Affiliative group cohesiveness	0.673	13.521	0.000*
Demand ability fit → Turnover intention	0.075	0.705	0.481

*significant

From table 4, it is found that the direct influence of the independent variable affiliation group cohesiveness has a negative and significant effect on TI as evidenced by the statistical t-value of 3.468 > t-estimated 1.96 or p-value 0.01 < 0.05 with a coefficient value of -0.347, meaning that the hypothesis is accepted. Demand ability fit significantly affects affiliation group cohesiveness based on the statistical t-value of 13,521 > t-estimated 1.96 or p-value 0.00 < 0.05 with a coefficient value of 0.637, meaning that the hypothesis is accepted. DAF does not affect TI based on the t-statistic value of 0.705 < 1.96 or p-values of 0.481 > 0.05 with a coefficient of 0.075, meaning that the hypothesis is rejected. In testing the indirect effect, explaining the analysis results through mediating variables is shown in table 5.

Table 5. Results of Indirect Effect Analysis

	Original Sample	T Statistic	P Values
Demand-ability-fit → Affiliative group cohesiveness → Turnover intention	-0.234	3.492	0.001

The results of the indirect effect test show that AGC mediates negatively and significantly between DAF and TI, as evidenced by the t-test results of 3.492 > 1.96 with a p-value of 0.001 < 0.05 coefficients -0.234, it can be concluded that AGC mediates effectively. There is a partial relationship between DAF and TI, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structural Equation Model Result

5. Discussion

The hypothesis test proves that DAF does not affect TI; this demonstrate is in line with the results of research conducted by Abdalla et al. (2018) and Choi et al. (2017) stated that there was no significant correlation between DAF and TI. Abdalla et al. (2018) explain that the

DAF lies in the work setting in the organization and the culture of each individual (Choi et al., 2017). This finding contradicts several previous studies, which state that DAF has an essential effect on TI. According to Park et al. (2012) and Bejer et al. (2019), DAF to be associated with task-related behaviors such as performance, stress, and turnover intention. DAF plays an important role in organizations, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, TI, and overall organizational performance (Kristof-Brown, 2005; Dineen et al., 2018). There is a low level of perception of DAF to change jobs. It takes a long time to increase DAF compared (Sylva et al., 2019). DAF achieved when individual contributions can meet the organization's demands or the environment (Sekiguchi, 2004). If a person's level of ability is too low, the work process, results, work efficiency, and quality of work will be lower; on the other hand, if the level of ability is too high, it is likely to be self-satisfied and disinterested in work (Cable and DeRue, 2002).

From the SET perspective, DAF affects group cohesiveness. This statement is in line with David et al. (2021) that DAF very important to maintain integrity and stability to support more stable social interactions. Furthermore, David et al. (2021) explained that the demand abilities fit also influenced by the conduciveness of the work environment. Bolino et al. (2010) support this opinion that SET between each group member can only occur in a cohesive group. Each group member can provide voluntary assistance and encourage each member to be directly involved in social exchange behavior. The findings of this study are in line with research by Seong et al. (2012), which states that DAF a positive effect on social cohesion and group performance (Seong et al., 2012) and also affect the quality of work and individual involvement in organizational activities (Crom et al., 2018). Job fit will create cohesiveness in unit work and make the unit work more functional (Werbel et al., 2001). According to Shin et al. (2009), group cohesiveness strengthens competence to achieve better group performance. AGC is an effort to build cooperative and socially binding relationships between group members marked by interest, a sense of belonging, and being part of a group to achieve common goals. According to SET, group cohesiveness is one of the organization's internal work environments and contributes to turnover intention (Gupta & Shaheen, 2017; Kang et al., 2017).

The hypothesis test found that AGC had a negative and significant effect on TI. The negative value of the coefficient of the AGC and TI variables indicates that the higher the level of AGC in the nurse's work unit, the lower the nurse's TI in the work unit. Nurses in carrying out their roles cannot be separated from teamwork. Group cohesiveness is one of the essential factors in team performance (Huang, 2009). Teams can become stronger and more successful if the environment in the organization is built cohesively (Al-Rawi, 2008; Lee et al., 2012). Cohesiveness impacts teamwork satisfaction to achieve the agreed goals (Bozic, 2018; Steinhardt, 2003). An organizational atmosphere with high cohesiveness has been shown to reduce turnover intention (Lee et al., 2012). Asegid et al. (2014) study show that group cohesiveness predicts TI. High group cohesiveness can reduce work-related stress (Guchait et al., 2016) and impact decreasing TI (Asegid et al., 2014). If group members do not feel an adequate level of cohesion, then there is a high probability that members will leave the organization (Boamah et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2012). This clearly shows that cohesive forces tend to remain in the work environment (Nwobia et al., 2017). The results revealed in

this study are that AGC negatively and significantly affects the DAF and TI of nurses working in type C private hospitals in South Sumatra meaning that the higher the level of DAF for nurses will affect the increase in AGC and have an impact on decreasing the TI of nurses at the hospital.

AGC mediating the influence between DAF and TI is possible because AGC is the central element that connects input and output in teamwork, determined by individual and task factors (Rafael et al., 2017). The DeOrtentiis study (2013) explains that AGC mediates the relationship between group member trust and group performance. The more cohesive the work atmosphere, the more trust, and group performance increase to strengthen competence in achieving better group performance (Shin et al., 2009). AGC seen as conformity in fulfilling job requirements, role expectations, and compliance with institutional norms (Abdalla, 2018). This can happen if individuals can meet the organization's demands in the form of contributions in terms of time, effort, commitment, knowledge, skills, and abilities (Kristof, 1996). Conformity occurs when individuals have the abilities needed to meet the demands of the environment and work and the ability to deal with stress or tension (Zacher et al., 2014).

6. Conclusion

This study increases the understanding of the TI of nurses working in private hospitals. The results of the study show that not all hypotheses are in line with the concepts and theories built. DAF positively affects turnover intention but has no significant effect on TI. AGC has been shown to mediate and significantly impact decreasing nurses' TI. It is hoped that nursing managers and organizational managers can use these findings to create a cohesive workgroup by increasing DAF to reduce TI. This finding is expected to inspire further research to explore more profound the role of AGC in building effective, productive, and efficient workgroups and can reduce TI.

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